

OFFICIATING AND SECURITY AS INDICES FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANISATION OF INTER-FACULTY SPORTS COMPETITION IN UNIVERSITY OF PORT HARCOURT, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study was designed to investigate the indices for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in the University of Port Harcourt with emphasis on officiating and security. Information was gathered through the use of a questionnaire to collate data from students in University of Port Harcourt. A total number of one hundred respondents were used for this study. Simple random sampling technique was used to sample the respondents. The results showed that there is need for adequate knowledge of the rules and regulations guiding every sport to be competed for by both the student-athletes and officials and also adequate security. Based on the findings, it is recommended that emphasis should be on knowledge of reviewed rules and regulations for every sport by officials while adequate security should be provided at competition venues to forestall any breakdown of law and order.

Keywords: officiating, security, effective organization, inter-faculty

1. Introduction

Sport is an athletic activity requiring skill, zero physical prowess and often of a competitive nature. Sports is one of the most important social concepts in the world today and many countries, organizations and institutions use sports as a tool for popularity, political, economic and diplomatic development (Ajiduah, 2001). Sports today is truly global in scope, and according to Duru (2001), sports is a unifying factor that unites human beings, regardless of race, gender class and other parameters. Morakinyo (2000) buttressed that sport constitutes a fundamental and extensive phase of culture all over the world. He explained further that, sports permeate many numbers of levels of contemporary society and touches upon and deeply influences such disparate elements as status, race, relation, business life, automotive design and so on and if these purposes

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are to be fully achieved, then the issue of organizing sport competition in the different facet of the society most importantly higher institutions in Nigeria is a thing that must be taken with the seriousness it deserves.

According to Onifade (1992), Sport in Nigeria higher institutions metamorphosed from the colonial period through independence to the present day. He submitted that the organization of sport in higher institutions in Nigeria has become a requirement that is backed by government policy and the pressure on the universities to fulfil the expectations of producing the nation's sportsmen and women have been on the increase. Audu (1998) opined that universities have consistently come under sharp criticism for failing in this regard and this accusation has centred mainly on over-concentration on academics with little or no cognizance for physical development through sport. Bucher and Krotee (2002) posited that our academics do not allocate any period for sport in their curricula. They argued that in other countries, university undergraduates are made to register for a certain number of courses in one form of sport or another.

2. Officiating

Sport has permeated the Nigerian society just as it was in many other societies worldwide (Aiyejuyo and Ayoade, 2002). The relevance and importance of sports makes sports management the bedrock for sports development in virtually all nations (Amuchie, 2002). According to Oloruntoba and Achugbu (2000), this is the aspect that is responsible for the smooth running of various sports in terms of planning, organizing, directing and controlling all essential inputs in sport. Therefore, sport succeed or fail in direct proportion to the appropriate decisions and actions of those responsible for managing them especially the officiating aspect which needs consistency and knowledge of changes in the rules and regulations guiding each sport more importantly in universities where students may go on rampage due to a poor decision by an official who may not be in tune with changes in a particular sport.

3. Security

Security in sport has taken centre stage due largely to the need to forestall any breakdown of law and order in and around the stadium before, during and after sporting events. Stadium invasions by fans and supporters as well as hurling of missiles at players/athletes during games may not only affect players/athletes performance but could also scare away sponsors and this would greatly affect the turnover of clubs and may eventually result into a low turnout at match venues by fans. Consequently, universities in Nigeria must put in place adequate security measures to curtail the excesses that may arise from poor officiating during faculty sports competition as this would encourage more students to participate in sport either as participant, spectator or fans.

4. Statement of the Problem

In recent times, sports events at the faculty level in the University of Port Harcourt is not as pronounced as it uses to be and this may not be unconnected with the skirmishes that usually characterize such events due largely to poor officiating and inability to guarantee the safety of students supporters. Therefore, this study examined the indices for the effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition at the University of Port Harcourt.

4.1 Research Questions

The study provides answers to the following questions:

- 1) Will officiating be an index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt?
- 2) Will security be an index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt?

4.2 Hypotheses

- 1) Officiating will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt.
- 2) Security will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt.

5. Methodology

Hypothesis 1: Officiating will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt.

Table 1: Chi-Square (χ^2) Table for the Responses on the Effect of Officiating on Effective Organisation of Inter-Faculty Sport Competition in University of Port Harcourt (N= 100)

	SA	A	D	SD	χ^2 Cal	χ^2 crit	Df	P
Poor officiating can cause violence in inter-hostel sport competition	19 19.0%	19 19.0%	38 38.0%	24 24.0%	24.41	12.59	6	.000
Spectators always go angry whenever officiating is bias	26 26.0%	41 41.0%	19 19.0%	14 14.0%				
Poor mastery of rules and regulations of games by officials can lead to violence in inter-faculty sports competition.	17 17.0%	43 43.0%	29 29.0%	11 11.0%				

The first null hypothesis tested at the 0.05 level of significance stated that officiating will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt. The result of the data was analysed with the use of Chi-square statistics (χ^2). The table above shows that χ^2 calculated value is 24.41 and χ^2 critical

value is 12.59, while the degree of freedom is 6 (c-1)(r-1). All questions testing this hypothesis has a level of significance less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). Since the χ^2 calculated value (24.41) is greater than χ^2 critical value (12.59), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted which stated that officiating will significantly be an index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis 2: Security will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt.

Table 2: Chi-Square (χ^2) Table for the Responses on the Effect of Security on the Organisation of Inter-Faculty Sport Competition in the University of Port Harcourt (N=100)

	SA	A	D	SD	χ^2 Cal	χ^2 crit	Df	P
Poor security leads to ineffectiveness in organization of inter-faculty sport competition	38 38.0%	44 44.0%	16 16.0%	2 2.0%	39.74	7.815	3	.000
Poor control of spectators can lead to ineffective inter-faculty sport competition	12 12.0%	28 28.0%	52 52.0%	8 8.0%				

The null hypothesis tested at the 0.05 level of significance stated that security will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt. The result of the data was analysed using Chi-square statistics (χ^2).

The table above shows that χ^2 calculated value is 39.74 and χ^2 critical value is 7.815, while the degree of freedom is 3 (c-1)(r-1). All questions testing this hypothesis has a level of significance less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$).

Since the χ^2 calculated value (39.74) is greater than χ^2 critical value (7.815), the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted which stated that security will be a significant indices for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt.

6. Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One

This stated that officiating will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt. The Chi-square revealed that hypothesis one was rejected. The reason being that the χ^2 calculated value (24.41) is greater than the χ^2 critical value (12.59).

This view is supported by Morakinyo (2000) when he pointed out that sport is a social phenomenon that has grown from its humble beginning of being an entertainment and recreation pastime to become a viable and prominent business phenomenon that

could no more be ignored in the social, political and economic environment of any nation. Sports succeed or fail in direct proportion to the appropriate decisions and actions of those responsible for managing them most importantly the officiating officials whose duties are to ensure fairness to the teams irrespective of their sympathy or support for a particular team.

Hypothesis Two

This stated that security will not be a significant index for effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in University of Port Harcourt. The Chi-square revealed that hypothesis two was rejected. The reason is that the χ^2 calculated value (39.74) is greater than the χ^2 critical value (7.815). This finding is in line with Bucher and Krotee (2002) who posited that efficient management of inter-faculty sport requires the establishment of sound security if it is to achieve its goals. Security serves as a standing plan for effective management of crowd of supporters before, during and after sports competition and inter-faculty competition in the universities is not an exception.

7. Conclusion

The study has shown that the problem of inter-faculty sport in the University of Port Harcourt may not be unconnected with poor officiating and inadequate security to secure competition venues and spectators as well as supporters who are most vulnerable and prone to attack in the event of any breakdown of law and order during inter-faculty sports competition. Therefore, the need for adequate security measures and knowledge of the rules and regulation guiding each sport becomes imperative.

7.1 Recommendations

Base on the foregoing, the following recommendations are hereby made:

- 1) Officiating officials that are up to date with periodic changes in their sport of engagement should be given the responsibility to officiate as this will enhance the effective organisation of inter-faculty sports competition in the University of Port Harcourt.
- 2) The universities should put in place adequate and effective security during inter-faculty sports competition to forestall breakdown of law and order.

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